

Minimally invasive implant rehabilitation in the esthetic zone: A case report of immediate implant and tooth preservation with a year radiological follow-up.

Sanjay Prasad

Professor & Head, Dept of Dentistry, College of Medicine & Sagore Dutta Hospital, Kolkata.

Abstract

This case report highlights a conservative and patient-centered approach to implant rehabilitation in the esthetic zone. A patient presented with concerns about a visible retained upper tooth and malformed adjacent tooth, causing esthetic dissatisfaction. Clinical examination revealed a retained root of the upper right first premolar and a malformed upper right second premolar, both suggestive of developmental anomalies.

The treatment planning was to extract only the retained root of the first premolar and place an immediate implant, while preserving the second premolar with a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown, avoiding the need for a second implant. Preoperative cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) imaging guided implant positioning, and postoperative CBCT confirmed precise implant placement. A radiological follow-up at one year demonstrated stable osseointegration, healthy peri-implant bone levels, and functional prosthesis with no complications.

This case underlines the importance of individualized treatment planning and clinical judgment in preserving tooth structure, optimizing esthetics, and minimizing surgical intervention. The use of immediate implant placement combined with conservative tooth restoration yielded a successful functional and esthetic outcome.

Keywords: CBCT, conservative treatment, developmental tooth anomaly, esthetic zone, immediate implant, retained premolar.

Address of correspondence: Dr Sanjay Prasad, Prof and Head, Dept of Dentistry, College of Medicine and Sagore Dutta Hospital, 578, B T Road, Kamarhati, Kolkata 700058.

Email address: - drsanjay1@gmail.com **Phone no:** 9434137806. **DOI:** 10.5281/zenodo.17049119

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Introduction

Implant-based rehabilitation has emerged as a gold standard for the replacement of missing teeth due to its high predictability, long-term success, and ability to restore both function and esthetics. With this in mind, it is important to establish sound clinical concepts with clearly defined parameters that lead to successful esthetics in the anterior maxilla, with long-term stability of the peri-implant tissues.^[1] Immediate implant placement has further enhanced treatment acceptance by reducing the number of surgical interventions, shortening treatment duration, and preserving alveolar bone and soft tissue architecture. Post-extraction implant

placement in this context refers to immediate placement (type 1), early placement with soft tissue healing (type 2), early placement with partial bone healing (type 3), and late placement (type 4).^[2] Particularly in the esthetic zone, where patient expectations are high, a well-executed implant procedure can significantly improve quality of life, self-confidence, and oral functionality.

However, in young patients—especially those with developmental dental anomalies such as malformed roots, congenitally missing teeth, or malformed crowns—treatment planning becomes more complex. The decision to extract and replace a tooth must be weighed against the potential for

preserving natural dentition, especially to save the patient of both money and discomfort. Moreover, anatomical limitations in such patients, such as altered root morphology or thin alveolar ridges, often necessitate a more cautious, case-specific approach.

Placement of implants in the posterior maxilla frequently poses a challenge due to the abundance of cases presenting with limited residual bone and reduced osseous density.^[3] Conservative treatment protocols that aim to preserve the natural tooth structure are increasingly being preferred, especially when esthetic considerations, functional stability, and patient age are taken into account. Modifying the coronal structure of malformed teeth and combining them with prudent restorative procedure can provide a balanced treatment strategy, reducing morbidity associated with multiple implant placements or autogenous bone harvesting.

In this case report, we present the management of a 25-year-old male patient with a retained upper right first premolar and a malformed second premolar. While the initial plan involved extraction of both premolars followed by dual implant placement, a re-evaluation led to a more conservative approach. Only the retained root was extracted and replaced with an immediate implant, while the adjacent malformed premolar was reshaped and restored with a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown. The treatment was guided by pre- and post-operative CBCT scans and was followed up for one year to assess radiological and clinical outcomes.

This case emphasizes the importance of individualized treatment planning and highlights how conservative techniques, when appropriate, can yield excellent functional and esthetic results while minimizing surgical intervention.

Case Presentation

A 25-year-old male patient reported to the dental clinic with a primary concern of unaesthetic appearance in his upper right premolar region, particularly noticeable during smiling. This concern was heightened by the fact that the patient was preparing for his upcoming marriage, and he desired an esthetically pleasing smile for the occasion. He reported no significant medical history and was otherwise systemically healthy.

Intraoral examination revealed a retained root in the region of the upper right first premolar (tooth 14) and a malformed crown of the adjacent second premolar (tooth 15). The retained root appeared discolored and clinically unesthetic, while tooth 15 exhibited a morphologically altered crown structure. The surrounding gingiva was healthy, with no signs of acute infection or periodontal compromise.

An intra-oral periapical (IOPA) radiograph and CBCT scan were advised to evaluate the extent of root retention, bone support, and overall anatomical considerations for implant planning. Radiographic findings confirmed the presence of a retained root in tooth 14 with sufficient surrounding bone for possible immediate implant placement. The crown of tooth 15, although malformed, showed divergent root, no periapical pathology, and good periodontal support, making it a candidate for restorative rehabilitation rather than extraction.

Based on the clinical and radiographic findings, a provisional diagnosis of retained root in tooth 14 and developmental anomaly affecting the crown of tooth 15 was established. The treatment objective focused on achieving functional and esthetic rehabilitation with minimal intervention, considering the patient's young age and esthetic expectations.

Treatment Procedure

The initial treatment plan involved the extraction of both the upper right first

premolar (tooth 14) and second premolar (tooth 15), followed by the placement of two dental implants to restore esthetics and function. However, upon careful reevaluation of clinical and radiographic findings, it was determined that the second premolar, despite its developmental malformation, had sufficient root structure and periodontal support. Hence, the treatment plan was modified to adopt a more conservative approach: only the retained root of tooth 14 would be extracted, and an immediate implant would be placed in the site, while tooth 15 would be preserved and modified for prosthetic restoration.

A preoperative CBCT scan done to judge bone height, width, and evaluate the proximity to any vital structure.^[4] The imaging confirmed adequate bone volume for immediate implant placement and helped guide surgical planning.

Under local anesthesia and strict aseptic conditions, the retained root of tooth 14 was extracted atraumatically using periostomes and elevators to minimize damage to the surrounding bone. Preservation of alveolar bone is the determining factor for aesthetic outcome as supracrestal tissues follow the resorption pattern of the underlying residual alveolar bone.^[5] A dental implant (Straumann) was then placed in the extraction socket with primary stability. The implant positioning was verified both clinically and with a postoperative CBCT.

The malformed crown of tooth 15 was conservatively prepared to allow for proper ferrule effect and support a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown. After an appropriate healing period, a screw-retained prosthesis was placed on the fixture abutment, and a PFM crown was cemented on tooth 15. This approach minimized surgical morbidity and achieved excellent functional and esthetic rehabilitation. The projected yearly failure rate of implants placed within extraction sockets was 0.82% (95% CI: 0.48–1.39%)

translating to a 2-year survival rate of 98.4% (97.3–99%).^[6] So immediate implant has high success rate and can be placed in predictable way provided all protocols are followed.

Outcome and Follow-Up

At one-year follow-up, clinical and radiological evaluation confirmed excellent implant stability, satisfactory bone levels, and healthy peri-implant tissues. The prosthesis remained functional and esthetically pleasing, with no signs of inflammation, discomfort, or prosthetic deliv.

Conclusion

This case illustrates how a conservative and customized approach can lead to successful functional and esthetic outcomes in implant dentistry. Preserving natural tooth structure and using advanced imaging and implant systems can significantly enhance treatment success, especially in young patients.

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FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

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Figure 8